

A NOTE ON THE CONSTITUTION OF HYPOPHOSPHORIC ACID AND ITS SALTS.

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This acid, having the empirical formula H_2PO_3 , has been the subject of long controversy with regard to its molecular constitution. From the available data, it is notable that as a general rule the dimeric formula $H_4P_2O_6$ has been derived by workers studying the free acid and its metallic salts and the monomeric H_2PO_3 by those working with organic derivatives.

Investigations on the Raman spectra of this acid and its derivatives have been scanty (Ghosh and Das, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 586), doubtless owing to preparative and other experimental difficulties. The results were incomplete and inconclusive. A thorough investigation was undertaken by the present authors but could not be completed in the present abnormal circumstances. Meanwhile, it could be seen that the data already obtained clarified a part of the question definitely, and are therefore being reported here.

Acid sodium hypophosphate was prepared by the method of Corne as modified by Rosenheim and Pinsker (*Ber.*, 1910, **43**, 2003). This salt crystallised well and was easily obtained pure, but was not very soluble in water. It was converted into the corresponding acid potassium salt through the sparingly soluble acid barium salt by double decomposition with potassium sulphate. An aqueous solution which was nearly of 55% strength was exposed to the mercury arc radiation $4358\text{\AA}$, using a *m*-dinitrobenzene filter, and the spectrum photographed with a fairly broad slit. A solution of the free acid was obtained through the insoluble lead salt and hydrogen sulphide, and concentrating over sulphuric acid. In this solution, the amount of sulphuric acid present as impurity was negligible, since the strongest breathing frequency of the sulphate ion was not found in the photographed spectrum.

The following Raman lines below 2000 cm^{-1} were recorded with the figures in brackets their approximate relative intensities, compared visually :—

Acid potassium salt : 300 (5), 468 (2), 661 (3), 896 (1), 1084 (4), 1204 (2).

Free acid solution : 300 (3), 475 (1b), 654 (2), 928 (1), 1093 (2), 1175 (1b).

The maximum number of Raman lines permissible for the monomeric formula PO_3'' , on the legitimate assumption that the three oxygen atoms are equivalent with respect to phosphorus, is *four*, corresponding to the

symmetry C_{2v} . It is therefore certain that the acid and its salt in solution contain more complex units. The closely analogous spectra of the acid and the acid salt show that the structures must be very similar. The dimeric *trans* structure seems highly probable for the two following reasons :—

(i) This structure having symmetry D_{2d} gives rise to six Raman frequencies.

(ii) The magnitude and relative intensities of the lines are closely comparable with those for the dithionate ion 275(4), 315(2), 550(1), 706(2), 1090(4), 1215(2b), being shown to possess this type of ionic symmetry by one of the present authors in a previous communication (Gupta and Guha, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1941, 7, 267).

It may be pointed out that an alternative explanation of the appearance of the six frequencies on viewing the HPO_3^- ion as a symmetrical top is untenable, on the ground that the acid phosphites do not give rise to more than four frequencies below 2000 cm^{-1} , where the ions are known to contain P-H link and possess unsymmetrical structures (Simon and Feher, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1937, 230, 289).

These results, interesting as they are, are yet insufficient to completely establish the structure of the acid and its derivatives, and a full discussion is deferred pending further work.

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Received May 23, 1942.

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